

The Ethical Views of Discord Users on Philosophy Discord Servers

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1. Limitations

What can a survey only answered by eight users tell us about the philosophical tendencies of Discord users on philosophy Discord servers? To be ambitious perhaps this could allow us to examine the very issues around experimental philosophy itself; as an anonymous Discord user stated of this very survey, “Experimental philosophy is nothing more than giving people philosophy quizzes. And giving philosophy quizzes is so lowly it is not even befitting of philosophy.” In some sense we could see much of experimental philosophy as asking people to take philosophy quizzes.

With this philosophy surveys are always limiting how a philosopher would want to answer particular questions, including questions in ethics. As one anonymous survey answerer told me, “some of the questions are kind of impossible to answer under certain ethical frameworks.” Ethics in a philosophical sense may need elaboration and a survey will almost limit one’s ethical framing. Another anonymous quote pointed to this very problem, “Do you not feel that this survey is strongly self-selecting certain results?” A further comment on this matter states, “most of those questions are false dichotomies.” No survey of ethics could properly capture an individual's ethical reality let alone the ethical reality of a survey group.

2. Survey Distribution

The survey was meant to be a quick eleven question survey to gather a general sense of how Discord users on philosophy servers thought about ethics. The survey was to be taken via a Google Forms link where users had to answer the form anonymously without collecting any data. This Google Forms link was posted on various philosophy Discord servers and sent to particular users via direct messages. Servers were considered to be philosophy servers if they stated themselves to be as such. The survey was up for two days, and data was automatically able to be catalogued via the systems offered by Google Forms.

3. Servers Frequented by Users

Each respondent to the forum was asked “What Philosophy Discord Server Do You Frequent The Most?” The forums that were mentioned as being frequented were as follows: Rational Animations, The Quarantine Collective thrice, La Borde, and The Philosophy Chat twice. One user responded to the survey verbatim, “What are you, a cop?” What this question shows despite the limited number of respondents is that there is a philosophy ecosystem on

Discord. And this creates a potential opportunity for philosophies to emerge within particular communities.

However, there did not seem to be data that correlated one's server to one's ethical viewpoints. So while there may be a philosophical ecosystem on Discord, it does not seem to be the case based on limited data that particular servers are absolutely echo chambering individuals. Even the response of "What are you, a cop?" shows a sense of possible rebellion against utter conformity within the Discord philosophical spaces.

4. Ethical Camps

Survey respondents were asked what ethical camp they feel under. I listed a host of options and also included another button so users could fill out for themselves what ethical camp they place themselves under. Survey respondents stated that they were in following ethical camps:

- 1 - Moral subjectivism
- 1 - Nietzschean-existential
- 1 - Deleuzo-Guattarian ethics of immanence
- 1 - Dialogue Philosophy
- 1- Consequentialist (non-utilitarian)
- 1 - Egoism
- 1 - Utilitarian

What this variety in and of ethical camp responses show is that even with a small sample size there are a wide range of ethical viewpoints within the Discord philosophy space. No user said they were part of the same ethical camp and multiple users said they were a part of camps that could be considered niche such as Deleuzo-Guattarian ethics of immanence.

5. Praxis, Theory, versus Abstraction

Survey takers were asked directly, "are your ethical standings more so a matter of theory, abstraction, or praxis." Users for this question could only pick from the three options of theory, abstraction, and praxis. While this is an imperfect and limiting question, it can give a general sense of how people conduct their ethical thinking. Six users ultimately answered that their ethics were a matter of praxis while one user each said their ethical standing was more so guided by theory and abstraction.

With this we could gather a potential sense that Discord users interested in philosophy see ethics as a practical matter. While it is possible for people to assume individuals who are interested in philosophy to be theoretical or abstraction based, but instead the survey group cares more so about ethics in practice.

6. Social or Personal Ethics

Survey takers were presented with the question, “is ethics more important on a personal level or a social level?” Perhaps this question was unfair, but here the idea was to gather if users thought the priority of ethics was to cultivate oneself or improve social conditions. Here the results landed on five users stating ethics was more important on a social level and three users stating ethics was more important on a social level. Aligning this question with the prior question, survey respondents for the most part find that ethics is best conducted as a matter of social praxis.

7. Local or Distant Ethics

Another three option question was presented which asked the following, “are we equally obligated to help those local or distant to us?” The options were yes, no we are more so obligated to help those local to us, and no we are more so obligated to help those distant to us. No survey respondents answered with ‘no we are more so obligated to help those distant to us.’ Six survey respondents answered ‘yes’ that we are equally obligated to help those local and distant to us. While two survey respondents answered ‘no we are more so obligated to help those local to us’.

There are some major weaknesses of this framing. The most obvious issue with this question is that what counts as local and distant is not specified. This leaves the respondent needing to interpret who counts as an individual that is local and distant to them.

8. Internal and External Factors in Ethics

Survey respondents answered evenly “are your ethics built more so by internal or external factors.” Here a binary question may not be fair. Given the dead even split on how this faulty binary question was answered there is no clear analysis that can be drawn from this on the ethical tendencies of Discord users on philosophical Discord servers.

9. Good, Bad, or Neutral

Survey takers were asked if individuals are born good, bad, or neutral. These are questions important to thinkers like Mozi and Xunzi. Seven of the eight survey respondents responded that people are born ethically neutral, with one respondent stating people are born naturally good. Here we can see a tendency that survey respondents believe ethics are developed over time and not innate to individuals, or at least not innate at birth.

10. Intent in Ethics

Takers of the survey were asked “does only intent matter in ethics, only results, or a mixture of both.” As was the case with the question on innate ethics, seven respondents stated

both intent along with results matter while one respondent answered only results matter. Here we can see Discord users on philosophy servers believe the weight of actions comes from multiple is measured by multiple means. We can then assert here that the majority of respondents are not consequentialists nor utilitarians. We could also potentially read into this question's response in conjunction with other responses that Discord philosophy server users as a general trend do not hold a simplified picture of ethics.

11. Nature or Nurture

For the presented question pertaining to nature and nurture I allowed for the entry of an 'other' option. The question went as follows, "is our understanding of ethics/morality built more so on nature or nurture?" Half of the respondents simply took the option of 'nurture.' One other respondent simply with 'nature'. Every other respondent presented custom results with go as follows.

"Neither and Both"

"Nature/Nurture cannot be divorced from one another."

"Ethics emerges through the interaction of human potential, lived experience, historical conditions, and existential becoming."

Here we have a tendency to reassert that the respondents in general do not think ethics is born in an innate process but a development over time.

12. The Trolley Problem

What sort of general ethics survey would be complete with a reference to the trolley problem. The question asked to survey takers was written as follows, "in the original trolley problem, is one held morally responsible for murder if they pull the switch?" Six users answered in the affirmative and two with the negative as the question was presented with a binary yes or no. This binary presentation of the question is limiting for all the flaws that come with that. Nonetheless we could read into this a sense that our respondents hold individuals responsible for their actions even in absurd and inordinate situations.

13. Conclusion

The final question asked was "have any of your ethical positions ever been changed by an engagement on a philosophy Discord server?" Here five users stated that they had an ethical position changed on a server engagement where three users answered 'no.' This final question was also presented in the binary.

Here we can assert that Discord is a plausible space of philosophical change. Yet, we can

certainly state that Discord is a space where philosophy can be engaged with in a niche and nuanced manner. While the survey itself failed to be properly nuanced survey respondents, no matter how limited they were, still revealed their nuance on ethical matters. What is likely the case is that there are individuals who are learning philosophy mainly through Discord philosophy servers. With this Discord over a forum for philosophical engagement and debate that can actually lead to philosophical development. It may be easy to dismiss online philosophy as lacking seriousness, yet even a faulty survey can reveal that there is philosophical depth in online space.

14. Funding

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